

Short academic bio

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Pia Carolla serves as the professor and chair of Byzantine Studies at the Department DIRAAS (Italian, Romance, Classical Studies, Visual & Performing Arts), University of Genoa.

With a focus on diplomacy & literature, she investigates Byzantine texts and manuscripts, as well as the Late Antique and Byzantine reception of Classics.

She is the Director of the series *Testi dell'Oriente greco tardoantico e bizantino*, Genova University Press (GUP) <<https://gup.unige.it/node/288>>.

Teaching

Byzantine Studies: in English, for beginners <<https://corsi.unige.it/en/off.f/2023/ins/67056>>;

Byzantine Philology: in Italian (& in English, on demand)
<<https://corsi.unige.it/en/off.f/2023/ins/67176>>

Byzantine Literature, in Italian (full reference in English)
<https://corsi.unige.it/en/off.f/2023/ins/67049>

The Icon and its Sources, in Italian (in English, on demand)
<<https://corsi.unige.it/en/off.f/2023/ins/66877>>

Fellowships

She is a member of the Doctoral Board in Classical and Modern Literatures and Cultures at the University of Genoa <<https://lccm.dottorato.unige.it/node/6>>

AISB Associazione Italiana di Studi Bizantini <<http://www.studibizantini.it/>>

CUBN Consulta Universitaria per la civiltà Bizantina e Neogreca:
member of the Central Board
<<http://www.studibizantini.it/consulte/cubn-consulta-universitaria-per-la-civiltà-bizantina-e-neogreca/>>

Academic collaborations/partnerships

- a) Univ. Tuebingen, Germany: seminars of the project *Malalas-Kommentar*
<<https://www.hadw-bw.de/forschung/forschungsstelle/malalas-kommentar>>

- b) Univ. Cologne (Koeln, Germany): digital project *DiBS. Creating a Sustainable Infrastructure for Research-Based Teaching in Byzantine Studies* <<https://dibs.uni-koeln.de/>>, Volkswagenstiftung
- c) Univ. Complutense Madrid, Comunidad de Madrid/Fondo Social Europeo: 2022-2024 conference *Instituciones en Ruinas. Corrupción y negatividad civil a la luz de la historia cultural y la filosofía social*, cluster GINEDIS <<https://www.ucm.es/grupos/grupo/798>> del Proyecto On Trust (H2019/HUM-5699), en colaboración con el proyecto anglo-alemán *Twisted Transfers. Discursive Constructions of Corruption in Ancient Greece and Rome* (AHRC AH/T012838/1) <<https://gtr.ukri.org/projects?ref=AH%2FT012838%2F1>>
- d) Univ. Pisa, Newcastle, Sorbonne, research team “Pompey’s New Order”, <<https://www.cfs.unipi.it/eventi/pompeys-new-order/>>
- e) Univ. Venice, Italy: international conferences *Il calamo della memoria*, 2023 (ongoing) <<https://www.unive.it/data/agenda/2/79109>>
- f) Univ. Roma2, Parma, Genoa: research center MAP - *Memoria delle Arti Performative* <<https://www-2023.centromap.uniroma2.it/>>

Selected publications

Bibliotheca Teubneriana

<<https://www.degruyter.com/document/doi/10.1515/9783110972412/html?lang=en>>

Renaissance Greek Manuscripts

<<https://www.degruyter.com/document/doi/10.1515/9783110366358-027/html?lang=en>>

Other contributions:

<<https://iris.unige.it/browse?authority=rp50891&type=author>>

Prizes

2022/2023 Label scientifico Università italo-francese (UIF/UFI L22A_18): international workshop “Retarder le temps. Pour une redatation des textes protochrétiens: questions de méthode et de composition. Ritardare il tempo. Per una ridatazione dei testi protocristiani: questioni di metodo e di composizione”, organised by Mauro Belcastro (UniTo), Pia Carolla (UniGe Diraas), Valérie Nicolet and Anna Van den Kerchov (*Institut protestant de théologie IPT*, Paris) <<https://diraas.unige.it/node/1830>>